

A HEXANUCLEAR Mn(II, III) PIVALATE CLUSTER WITH A {Mn₆O₂} CORE

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Abstract

A new [Mn₆O₂(O₂CCMe₃)₁₀(HO₂CCMe₃)(EtOH)₃]·EtOH hexanuclear mixed-valent coordination compound with a {Mn₆O₂} core has been synthesized and characterized by single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis. The central mixed-valence [Mn^{II}₄Mn^{III}₂(μ₄-O₂)]¹⁰⁺ core consists of six Mn centers, two Mn^{III} and four Mn^{II} ions, arranged as two edge-sharing flattened Mn₄ tetrahedra, with a μ₄-O²⁻ ion in the center of each tetrahedron. Peripheral ligation is provided by pivalate and ethanol groups.

1. Introduction

Hexanuclear [Mn₆O₂(O₂CR)₁₀L₄] clusters (where L = neutral monodentate ligand and R = Me, Et, CHMe₂, CMe₃) with a central {Mn^{III}₂Mn^{II}₄(μ₄-O)₂} core is the most fascinating Mn oxo-carboxylate clusters used as building blocks in construction of coordination networks [1]. First, the topology of the cluster skeleton remains unchangeable, RCO₂⁻ carboxylate and capping ligands can be modified. Second, four capping ligands L in these clusters can be completely or partially replaced; thus, [Mn₆O₂(O₂CR)₁₀] clusters can be considered as building blocks with connectivity up to four. A detailed analysis of hexanuclear [Mn₆O₂(O₂CR)₁₀L₄] compounds extracted from the Cambridge Structural Database (ConQuest Version 1.19, CSD version 5.38) shows that there are more than 229 examples of these hexanuclear Mn-containing compounds with a {Mn^{III}₂Mn^{II}₄(μ₄-O)₂} core in which R = Me, Et, CHMe₂, CMe₃.

Note that the first 1D coordination polymers based on the {Mn₆O₂} carboxylate building blocks—[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCMe₃)₁₀(HO₂CCMe₃)₂(4,4'-bpy)]_n—were obtained by Yamashita et al. in 2002 [2]. Later on, {[Mn₆O₂(O₂CET)₁₀(H₂O)₄]·2(EtCO₂H)}_n [3] and {[Mn₆O₂(O₂CMe)₁₀(H₂O)₄]·2.5(H₂O)}_n [4], in which {Mn₆} building clusters are connected into 1D networks by shorter linkers, were prepared. In 2010, three new 1D coordination polymers {[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCMe₃)₁₀(Me₃CCO₂H)(EtOH)(na)]·EtOH·H₂O}_n, {[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCHMe₂)₁₀(pyz)₃]·H₂O}_n and {[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCHMe₂)₁₀(Me₂CHCO₂H)(EtOH)(bpe)]·Me₂CHCO₂H}_n (where pyrazine (pyz), nicotinamide (na), and 1,2-bis(4-pyridyl)ethane (bpe)) were reported [5].

The formation of 2D layers based on a hexanuclear {Mn₆O₂} carboxylate motif was first reported by Ovcharenko et al. in 2013. Two new coordination polymers—{[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCMe₃)₁₀(ina)₂]·3(Me₂CO)}_n and {[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCMe₃)₁₀(ina)₂]·2(EtOAc)}_n—were prepared using N,O-donor bridging ligands, such as isonicotinamide (ina) [6]. Employing ina and N,N'-donor aldrithiol (adt-4) spacer ligands in the reaction, new 2D coordination polymers [Mn₆O₂(O₂CCMe₃)₁₀(ina)₂]_n, {[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCMe₃)₁₀(adt-4)₂]·2(thf)}_n and {[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCHMe₂)₁₀(adt-4)₂]·(thf)·3(EtOH)}_n were also synthesized [7].

Recently, a new series of hexanuclear mixed-valent $\{\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2\}$ -containing pivalate and isobutyrate clusters $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_{10}(\text{Me}_3\text{CCO}_2\text{H})_3(\text{EtOH})] \cdot (\text{Me}_3\text{CCO}_2\text{H})$, $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_{10}(\text{Me}_3\text{CCO}_2\text{H})_2(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot 2(\text{EtOH})$, and $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_{10}(\text{Me}_3\text{CCO}_2\text{H})_2(\text{MeOH})_2] \cdot 2(\text{MeOH}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and coordination polymers that incorporate these clusters, namely, $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCHMe}_2)_{10}(\text{pyz})(\text{MeOH})_2]_n$, $\{[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCHMe}_2)_{10}(\text{pyz})_{1.5}(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 0.5(\text{H}_2\text{O})\}_n$, and $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_{10}(\text{HO}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_2(\text{en})]_n$ have been synthesized (where pyz = pyrazine, en = ethyl nicotinate) [8]. As an extension of the previous study on the synthesis of oxo-bridged polynuclear hexanuclear Mn(III, II) containing clusters, herein the synthesis and X-ray characterization of a new hexanuclear $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_{10}(\text{HO}_2\text{CCMe}_3)(\text{EtOH})_3] \cdot \text{EtOH}$ (**1**) pivalate cluster compound are reported.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials, methods, and X-ray crystallography

All reactions were run under aerobic conditions using chemical and solvents as received without further purification. The $\text{Mn}(\text{Me}_3\text{CCO}_2)_2$ precursor compound was prepared as described in [9]. A Bandelin Sonorex RK-100H ultrasonic bath operating at 45 kHz with a maximum power output of 160 W was used for the ultrasonic irradiation.

X-ray data were collected at room temperature on an Oxford Diffraction Xcalibur diffractometer equipped with a CCD area detector and a graphite monochromator utilizing MoK_α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Final unit cell dimensions were determined and refined on an entire dataset. All calculations to solve the structures and refine the proposed models were carried out with the SHELX suite of programs [10]. The C-bounded H-atoms were placed in calculated positions and treated using a riding model approximation with $U_{\text{iso}}(\text{H}) = 1.5U_{\text{eq}}(\text{C})$ for methyl group and $1.2U_{\text{eq}}(\text{C})$ for other hydrogen atoms, while the oxygen-bounded H-atoms were found from differential Fourier maps and isotopically refined with isotropic displacement parameter $U_{\text{iso}}(\text{H}) = 1.5U_{\text{eq}}(\text{O})$. The X-ray data and the details of the refinement for **1** are summarized in Table 1; the selected geometric parameters are given in Tables 2 and 3. The figures were drawn using the Mercury program. Crystallographic data of the new compound reported herein was deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre and allocated the deposition number CCDC 1972569.

2.2. Synthesis

Synthesis of $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_{10}(\text{HO}_2\text{CCMe}_3)(\text{EtOH})_3] \cdot \text{EtOH}$ (1**).** $\text{Mn}(\text{Me}_3\text{CCO}_2)_2$ (0.10 g, 0.38 mmol) and N-phenyldiethanolamine (0.018 g, 0.09 mmol) were dissolved in an EtOH/ CH_2Cl_2 mixture (4 mL/4 mL). The resulting brown solution was treated in an ultrasonic bath for 30 min. The solution was filtered off and allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature. Brown crystals of **1** suitable for X-ray measurements were obtained within 1 week, washed with EtOH, and dried in air. Yield (based on Mn): 0.064 g, 60 %.

3. Results and Discussion

The reaction of manganese(II) pivalate with N-phenyldiethanolamine in an EtOH/ CH_2Cl_2 mixture results in a new hexanuclear compounds with a stable $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_{10}]$ unit, while comprising a coordinated neutral monodentate ligand: one pivalic and three ethanol molecules in

[Mn₆O₂(O₂CCMe₃)₁₀(HO₂CCMe₃)(EtOH)₃] \cdot EtOH (**1**).

X-ray analysis showed that the cluster contains a {Mn^{II}₄Mn^{III}₂O₂}¹⁰⁺ core of two edge sharing Mn₄ tetrahedra with a μ_4 -O²⁻ ion in the center of each tetrahedron. Peripheral ligation is provided by ten bridging pivalate monoanionic ligands (Fig. 1a). Four of them coordinate in a μ_3 -mode and bridge three Mn centers, whereas each of the other six bridges two Mn centers in a μ_2 -mode.

The shortest intracluster Mn^{III}₁-Mn^{III}₂ distance, being 2.8108(11) Å, is formed by two Mn^{III} ions that occupied the common edge of the Mn₄ tetrahedra, with a μ_4 -O₂⁻ ion in the center of each tetrahedron. All other Mn^{III}-Mn^{II} and Mn^{II}-Mn^{II} bond distances in Mn₄ tetrahedra are longer (3.145(2)–3.169(1) and 3.720(2)–4.837(1) Å, respectively). In **1**, two peripheral Mn atoms (Mn₅ and Mn₆) in Mn₄ tetrahedra are additionally capped by ethanol molecules. Two peripheral Mn atoms in the second Mn₄ tetrahedra (Mn₃ and Mn₄) are capped by ethanol and pivalic acid molecules. All Mn^{II} atoms have a near-octahedral surrounding. The Mn^{III} ions (Mn₁ and Mn₂) have an elongated octahedral MnO₆ environment. The axial and equatorial Mn^{III}-O bond distances are in the range of 2.211(2)–2.275(5) and 1.883(4)–1.978(2) Å, respectively. Selected bond distances are summarized in Table 2. Four terminal Mn atoms are in the lower oxidation state +2 and have longer Mn–O_{carb} bond distances ranging from 2.333(5) to 2.370(6) Å. Analysis of the mode of packing of the components revealed a system of inter- and intramolecular O–H...O hydrogen bonds in **1** (Fig. 1b, Table 3). The coordinated pivalic acid forms a short intramolecular hydrogen bond O(24)–H(24)...O(22) of 2.559(8) Å with the bridging pivalate. The solvent EtOH molecule forms intermolecular O–H...O hydrogen bonds (2.59(3), 2.65(4), and 2.73(2) Å) with the coordinated EtOH and pivalate molecules from {Mn₆} cluster.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for **1**

Empirical formula	C ₆₇ H ₁₂₆ Mn ₆ O ₃₀	<i>V</i> , Å ³	2265.4(3)
Formula weight	1741.31	<i>D</i> _{calc} (g/cm ⁻³)	1.276
<i>T</i> (K)	293(2)	μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.880
Crystal system	Triclinic	<i>F</i> (000)	918
Space group	<i>P</i> -1	Crystal size (mm)	0.50 \times 0.50 \times 0.40
<i>Z</i>	1	Reflections collected/unique	3.112 / 25.048
<i>a</i> , Å	13.5932(7)	Reflections with <i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)	15038
<i>b</i> , Å	14.0742(7)	Data/restraints/parameters	10367 / 252 / 917
<i>c</i> , Å	15.2032(9)	Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.001
α (°)	114.592(5)	<i>R</i> ₁ , <i>wR</i> ₂ [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0438, 0.1151
β (°)	90.231(5)	<i>R</i> ₁ , <i>wR</i> ₂ (all data)	0.0543, 0.1240
γ (°)	117.874(5)	$\Delta\rho_{\max}$, $\Delta\rho_{\min}$, (e \cdot Å ⁻³)	0.586 and -0.298

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Molecular structure (a) and fragment of crystal packing (b) in **1**. Color code: Mn is denoted by purple spheres; O, red balls; C, grey sticks; and H, grey lines.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) for **1**

Mn(1)-O(1)	1.888(4)	Mn(4)-O(7)	2.140(5)
Mn(1)-O(2)	1.880(4)	Mn(4)-O(9)	2.334(5)
Mn(1)-O(8)	2.250(5)	Mn(4)-O(25)	2.257(6)
Mn(1)-O(16)	1.951(4)	Mn(5)-O(2)	2.180(4)
Mn(1)-O(18)	2.229(4)	Mn(5)-O(8)	2.322(5)
Mn(1)-O(21)	1.967(4)	Mn(5)-O(10)	2.152(5)
Mn(2)-O(1)	1.901(4)	Mn(5)-O(13)	2.122(6)
Mn(2)-O(2)	1.896(4)	Mn(5)-O(15)	2.154(4)
Mn(2)-O(6)	1.949(4)	Mn(5)-O(26)	2.251(5)
Mn(2)-O(9)	2.246(5)	Mn(6)-O(2)	2.177(4)
Mn(2)-O(11)	1.952(5)	Mn(6)-O(12)	2.126(5)
Mn(2)-O(19)	2.240(5)	Mn(6)-O(14)	2.143(6)
Mn(3)-O(1)	2.160(4)	Mn(6)-O(17)	2.129(5)
Mn(3)-O(3)	2.101(5)	Mn(6)-O(19)	2.371(5)
Mn(3)-O(18)	2.325(5)	Mn(6)-O(27)	2.259(6)
Mn(3)-O(20)	2.090(5)	Mn(1)-Mn(2)	2.811(1)
Mn(3)-O(22)	2.218(4)	Mn(1)-Mn(3)	3.155(1)
Mn(3)-O(23)	2.256(5)	Mn(1)-Mn(5)	3.145(1)
Mn(4)-O(1)	2.176(4)	Mn(2)-Mn(4)	3.169(1)
Mn(4)-O(4)	2.137(5)	Mn(2)-Mn(6)	3.165(1)
Mn(4)-O(5)	2.128(5)		

Table 3. Selected hydrogen bonds (Å) for **1**

D-H...A	d(D-H)	d(H...A)	d(D...A)	∠(DHA)	Symmetry transformation for A
O(24)-H(24)...O(22)	0.82	1.75	2.559(8)	169	x, y, z
O(25)-H(25D)...O(28A)	0.85	2.04	2.65(4)	129	x, y, z
O(26)-H(26A)...O(30)	0.85	2.21	2.73(2)	120	x+1, y, z
O(27)-H(27A)...O(29A)	0.85	1.98	2.59(3)	128	x, y+1, z

4. Conclusions

A new $[\text{Mn}_6\text{O}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCMe}_3)_{10}(\text{HO}_2\text{CCMe}_3)(\text{EtOH})_3]\cdot\text{EtOH}$ hexanuclear mixed-valent coordination compound with a $\{\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}_2\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}_4(\mu_4\text{-O})_2\}$ core has been synthesized and characterized by single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis. The synthesized mixed-valent hexanuclear carboxylate manganese coordination cluster can be used as a supramolecular building block and offers additional possibilities for crystal engineering of new interesting materials with high porosity and magnetic properties and new avenues to be explored.

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